

AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE IMPACT OF WOMEN EDUCATION ON THE FAMILY'S SOCIO-ECONOMIC SUSTAINABILITY IN JOS NORTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF PLATEAU STATE

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ABSTRACT: There is a common assertion that if you educate a woman, you educate a nation. In recent times, women education has received government, non-governmental bodies, scholars and researchers with many studies geared towards improving the standard of women education. In order to determine whether women education can contribute meaningfully to the socio-economic development of the society, this research paper was prompted to investigate the impact of women education on the socio-economic status of the family in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State. Four research questions and four hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Descriptive survey research was adopted in the study. Questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. The data collected in the study was analysed using mean score. From the analysis of data, collected, the findings of the study revealed that educating women can contribute to family income, it can improve the educational development of the society and also improve the standard of child upbringing of children in the family, it can contribute to the standard of income in the family, it can help women to be gainfully employed and can improve the standard of living in the family and can improve the standard of child-care in the family, it can improve the extent to which women support their children's education and can also improve the standard of academic achievement of their children in school. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that mass enlightenment campaign should be carried out by government and non-governmental organisations to encourage Nigerian women who are not educated to enroll in school. It was also recommended that more adult education centres should be established especially in rural areas and the Nigerian government should show more commitment to women education by making it free from primary to tertiary education level.

Keywords: Education, Family, Socio-Economic, Sustainability, Income, Up-bringing.

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INTRODUCTION

Socioeconomic status (SES) is an economic and sociological combined measure of a person's work experience and of an individual's or family's economic access to resources and social position in relation to others. When analyzing a family's SES, the household income, parents' educational level and occupation are examined (Okojie, 2021). A family's socioeconomic status (SES) describes their level of education, access to and control over economic and social resources relative to that of other families. Family's SES has been recognized as an important determinant of a family's sustainability. Socio-economic sustainability of a family refers to how families over long period of time are able to maintain their level of economic well-being (Abiri,

2021). It combines educational, financial, economic and social position of a family in relation to other families. It is usually measured based on income, education and occupation. Socioeconomic sustainability is typically broken into three categories, high, middle and low to describe the three areas a family or an individual may fall using these three variables; income, education, and occupation (Osuaata, 2017).

Families with low socioeconomic sustainability often lack the financial, social, and educational supports that characterize families with high socioeconomic sustainability. Such families also may have inadequate or limited access to community resources that promote and support their children's educational development. All over the world, education is recognized as cornerstone for sustainable development (Okwu, 2021).

According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014), the purpose of education is to equip the Nigerian citizens with skills to reshape their society, eliminate inequality and foster socio-economic development of the individuals. In the last two decades, the sustainability of women and need to emancipate them into active partnership within the socio-economic development processes have dominated the discourse at National and International workshops, seminars, and conferences. The problems of women opportunities for education looms larger at the turn of twenty-first century in Africa and women represents two thirds of the world uneducated population (Abonyi et al., 2014). However, for women to be integrated into development processes, they need quality education, in order to become co-partners in national and socio-economic development.

The importance of literacy and women empowerment in promoting equality and the advancement of women was further stressed by the Millennium Development Goals MDG's (2011), the Education for All (EFA) and Dakar Goals (2000), Olomukoro (2021) opined that the objective of the sustainable development goal five was ensure full integration of women into the social and political sphere as a means of developing the nation's human resources for national and socio-economic development. Its objectives included the promotion of gender main streaming into all policies and programmes. Access to women educational development programmes, in the words of Kagiticbias Goksen and Gulgoz (2015), is considered one of the main factors for women empowerment and National development. However, Ifedili and Ifedili (2022), assert that Nigerian women are stalled by culture, which makes them vulnerable to effectively join the workforce and contribute to socio-economic and thus national development.

Furthermore, United Nation (2020) stated that women alone constitute one half of the world's population and earn one tenth of the world's income. They also won hundredth of the world's property including land. This buttressed the fact that women have so far benefited very little or nothing despite contributing much from the economic resources accruing in the society. According to World Development Report (2021) only about 7.3% of women are occupying political positions. Infact, in some Nigerian societies in eastern and northern Nigeria, women do not have right to inherit property talk more of contesting elections. For instance in most states of northern Nigeria, some female children have been relegated to hawking and later sent into early marriage as early as from the age of twelve (Ochonogor, 2015). Similarly, in the eastern and southern part of Nigeria, some girls engaged in commercial sex to make ends meet. Many are exported to foreign countries to attract international client as prostitutes. Consequently, they are often prone to the vulnerability of HIV/AIDS diseases (Ifedili & Ifedili, 2022).

According to Patrinos (2020), the opportunity cost of not investing in girls and women education in Nigeria is between 1.2% and 1.5% in missed GDP growth. Thus, the incentive to invest in women education goes up because it contributes immensely in moving a country out of

extreme poverty. In addition to total economic growth, women's education also increases the equitability of the distribution of wealth in a society. Increased women's education is important for achieving this as it targets the impoverished women, a particularly disadvantaged group. There is also evidence that lower gender disparity in educational attainment for a developing country correlates with lower overall income disparity within the society.

Women's education leads to significant social development. Some of the most notable social benefits include decreased fertility rates and lower infant mortality rates and lower maternal mortality rates (Ochonogor, 2015). Closing the gender gap in education also increases gender equality, which is considered important both in itself and because it ensures equal rights and opportunities for people regardless of gender. Women's education has cognitive benefits for women as well. Improved cognitive abilities increase the quality of life for women and also lead to other benefits. One example of this is the fact that educated women are better able to make decisions related to health, both for themselves and their children. Cognitive abilities also translate to increased political participation among women (Patrionos, 2020). There are also benefits relating to the woman's role in the family. Educated women are more involved in the decision-making process of the family and report making more decisions over a given time period. In particular, these benefits extend to economic decisions. Besides the intrinsic value of increasing a woman's agency, having women play a more active role in the family also brings about social benefits for family members. In a household where the mother is educated, children and especially girls are more likely to attend school (Okojie, 2021).

Furthermore, educated women have been associated with high family income resulting in high standard of living in the family. They are also known to improve the standard of child-care in the family resulting in low infant mortality and good hygiene in the family. Research by Opaluwah (2021) also linked women's education to good children's educational development. Opaluwah discovered that educated women help their children with their academic work at home thus resulting in higher educational achievement of such children. Based on findings from previous studies, this research paper will investigate whether women's education also contributes to the family's socio-economic sustainability in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State.

Statement of the Problem

Over the years, inequality of educational accessibility has been hindering women participation in socio-economic development of Nigeria. Salako (2019) asserts that the political culture that has emerged from the colonial orientation has been particularly patriarchal. It reflects gender inequalities in men and women's roles, and levels the access to state power, resources and institutions (Adebusyi, 2021). In addition, specific development involved have been immensely ineffective in the state. This is also juxtaposed by poor state controlled developmental programmes which have helped to erode independent feminist initiative ever geared towards women educational progression in our society.

Women access to formal education in Nigeria is still being constrained to their unfair and unacceptable domestic workload. Based on this, the realization of the Sustainable Development Goals, gender equality and women empowerment is continuously being hindered (Opaluwah, 2021). Osuata (2017) and Abiri (2021) investigated the causes of poor women education in Nigeria, however, none of the reviewed studies have linked socio-economic status and women's education. This study has established that gap and intends filling the gap by investigating the

impact of women’s education on family socio-economic sustainability in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- What is the extent to which women’s education contributes to family socio-economic sustainability?
- What is the extent to which women’s education improves the standard of family’s income?
- What is the extent to which women’s education improves the standard of children’s educational development in the family?

METHOD AND PROCEDURE

Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study and it guided the researcher in investigating how women’s education influences socio-economic sustainability of the family in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State. The sample for the research consists of a total of 400 women selected across ten wards in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State. In selecting the sample for this research, the researcher made use of the simple random sampling technique. The instrument used in this research for the purpose of data collection was a questionnaire. To establish the reliability of the instrument, it was pilot-tested in other ward aside from the one sampled for the study. The Cronbach Alpha Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the internal consistency of the two instruments using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22. The computed reliability coefficient was 0.85 which implies that the instrument was adequately reliable for the conduct of the research. The data collected in this research was subjected to analysis through the use of mean and standard deviation. The data that were collected from the respondents in the study were used to answer the research questions drawn for the study.

RESULTS

Research Question One: How does women’s education contributes to family socio-economic sustainability?

Table 1: Women’s education contribution to family socio-economic sustainability

s/n	Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	Educating women can contribute to family income	239	61	-	58	42	3.99	Agree
2	Educating women can improve the educational development of the society	248	52	-	30	70	3.94	Agree
3	Educating women can improve the standard of child upbringing of children in the family	258	42	-	40	60	3.99	Agree
Grand Mean							3.97	Agree

The results from the analysis (Table 1) of research question one show the statement on whether educating women can contribute to family income was rated with a mean score of 3.99. The next statement on whether educating women can improve the educational development of the society was rated with a mean score of 3.94 and was agreed with. The following statement on whether educating women can improve the standard of child upbringing of children in the family was rated with a mean score of 3.99 and was agreed with. The grand mean of 3.97 revealed that women's education contribution to family socio-economic sustainability.

Research Question Two: How does women's education improves the standard of family's income?

Table 2: Women's education improvement of family income

s/n	Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Decision
4	Educating women can contribute to the standard of income in the family	231	69	-	34	66	3.91	Agree
5	Educating women can help them to be gainfully employed	235	65	-	48	52	3.95	Agree
6	Educating women can improve the standard of living in the family	240	60	-	37	63	3.94	Agree
Grand Mean							3.93	Agree

The results from the analysis (Table 2) of research question two shows that from the statement on whether educating women can contribute to the standard of income in the family was rated with a mean score of 3.91 and was agreed with. The next statement on whether educating women can help them to be gainfully employed was rated with a mean score of 3.95 and was agreed with. The last statement on whether educating women can improve the standard of living in the family was rated with a mean score of 3.94 and was agreed with. Evidence from the result of the grand mean (3.93) revealed that women's education improve family income.

Research Question Three: How does women's education contributes to children's educational development in the family?

Table 3: Women's education contributes to children's educational development in the family

s/n	Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Decision
7	Educating women can improve the standard of children's education in the family	148	152	-	53	47	3.75	Agree
8	Educated women help their children with their academic work at home	158	142	-	20	80	3.69	Agree
9	Educated women create better future prospects for their children	131	169	-	34	66	3.66	Agree
Grand Mean							3.70	Agree

The results from the analysis of research question three shows that the responses on the extent to which women's educational can promote children's educational development. The statement on whether educating women can improve the standard of children's education in the family was rated with a mean score of 3.75 and was therefore agreed with. The following statement on

whether educated women help their children with their academic work at home was rated with a mean of 3.69 and was agreed with. The last statement on whether educated women create better future prospects for their children was rated with a mean of 3.66 and was agreed with. The grand mean (3.70) revealed that women's education contributes to children's educational development in the family.

DISCUSSION

Research question one on the extent to which women's education contributes to family socio-economic sustainability is analysed. From the analysis of data collected, it was discovered that educating women can contribute to family income, it can improve the educational development of the society and also improve the standard of child upbringing of children in the family. This finding is in conformity with the findings of Abiona (2013) who discovered that women participation in educational programmes in Nigeria is barely at an average level and therefore need to be improved upon.

Research question two on the extent to which women's education can contribute to family income is analysed. From the analysis of data collected, it is observed that educating women can contribute to the standard of income in the family, it can help women to be gainfully employed and can improve the standard of living in the family. This finding corroborates the findings of Ezeomah (2022) who discovered that educating women can empower women to contribute immensely to economic and social development of the family by improving family income, parental education and chances of parents getting into prestigious occupations.

Findings from the analysis of research question three revealed that educating women can improve the standard of children's education in the family; educated women can help their children with their academic work at home and create better future prospects for their children. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Olomukoro (2021) who discovered that maternal education can improve academic success of their children

CONCLUSION

Over the years, inequality of educational accessibility has been hindering women participation in socio-economic development of the family in Nigeria. However, it was discovered from the findings of this study that women's education contributes to the standard of family income, women's education improves the standard of family's socio-economic sustainability and also enhances the standard of children's education in the family. It was therefore concluded that there is a great impact of women education on the family's socio-economic sustainability in Jos North Local Government Area of Plateau State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are thereby made:

- Mass enlightenment campaign should be carried out by government and non-governmental organisations to encourage Nigerian women who are not educated to enroll in school and more adult education centres should be established especially in rural areas

- Government should show more commitment to women education by making it free from primary to tertiary education level
- Women education trust fund should be established by the government to finance the education of girls and women from low socio-economic background.

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